

Optimizing Network Services with Quantum Dynamic Programming and Grover’s Search

Engin Zeydan*, Josep Mangués-Bafalluy*, Yekta Turk[◇], Abdullah Aydeger[^], Madhusanka Liyanage[⌘]

*Centre Tecnològic de Telecomunicacions de Catalunya (CTTC), Spain, [◇]Aselsan Corp., Turkey

[^]College of Engineering and Science, Florida Institute of Technology

[⌘]Network Softwarization and Security Labs (NetsLab), University College Dublin, Ireland.

Email: {engin.zeydan, josep.mangués} @cttc.cat, yektaturk@aselsan.com, aaydeger@fit.edu, madhusanka@ucd.ie

Abstract—As network service requirements and computational complexity continue to increase, efficient resource management and optimization techniques are essential to ensure performance and scalability. In the context of edge cloud networks, there are computational challenges associated with optimal path selection and resource allocation. This paper explores the integration of quantum computing with dynamic programming (DP) to solve path optimization problems in network service orchestration. More specifically, we investigate two approaches to DP: the classical DP method, which provides exact solutions by systematically evaluating all possible states, and a quantum-enhanced version, which uses the Grover search algorithm to accelerate for performance comparisons in terms of accuracy and execution times. Simulation results provide insights into the comparative performance of classical and quantum DP approaches, with an emphasis on search time improvements. Beyond computational performance, we discuss practical considerations including the constraints of current quantum hardware, algorithmic efficiency improvements, scalability challenges, and integration with classical systems. Additionally, we evaluate energy efficiency, cost-benefit trade-offs, resilience, and regulatory concerns associated with quantum-enabled service orchestration.

Index Terms—Grover search, network orchestration, dynamic programming, network services, optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

As modern networks become ever larger and more complex, efficient service orchestration and resource management are becoming increasingly important. The proliferation of edge cloud infrastructures driven by low-latency applications, dynamic workload allocation and real-time decision making has brought new challenges in optimizing service paths, managing network resources and ensuring fault tolerance. Traditional Dynamic Programming (DP) algorithms have long been utilized for solving optimization problems in such environments; however, as network sizes and constraints grow, these classical methods often become computationally intractable due to their exponential time complexity in large search spaces. Quantum computers offer a promising approach to speeding up search

and optimization problems, especially through algorithms such as Grover search, which can offer a quadratic speedup over classical brute force approaches. Grover’s search algorithm is a quantum algorithm that finds the desired element in an unsorted database with quadratic acceleration compared to the classical algorithm [1]. Theoretically, Grover’s algorithm scales much better than linear search as the size of the array increases, providing quadratic speedup. It is used in various quantum algorithms where a quadratic speedup is advantageous. Its complexity is $O(\sqrt{N})$. Quantum counting combines the Grover algorithm with quantum phase estimation to count the number of solutions to a search problem. It provides the same quadratic speedup of the search, but provides additional information about the number of solutions [2]. Its complexity is again $O(\sqrt{N})$. Shor’s algorithm is not a search algorithm in the strict sense, but it is important in the context of quantum acceleration. It provides an exponential speed-up for certain problems such as the factorization of integers, where classical algorithms have an exponential time complexity [3]. Its complexity is polynomial time for the integer factorization. An overview of quantum search algorithm in the wireless communication domain is provided in [4].

The state of the art in network management optimization for the edge-cloud continuum focuses on several key areas relevant to our work. For multi-agent and path-aware approaches, recent research has introduced novel algorithms that utilize path-aware heuristics to opportunistically process application requests across the edge-cloud continuum. These approaches aim to reduce the demand of the network core and minimize the end-to-end latency [5], [6]. For multi-criteria optimization, control and optimization techniques are being applied to develop tools for optimizing the management of the edge-to-cloud continuum. These methods consider multiple criteria to balance various performance objectives [7], [8]. For task allocation frameworks, optimization frameworks are developed that are specifically designed for task allocation in the edge/hub/cloud continuum [9], [10]. These frameworks address the challenges of distributing tasks across different layers of the network infrastructure. For cloud-native implementations and end-to-end monitoring, experimental frameworks are being developed to manage 5G and beyond networks through cloud-native implementations and comprehensive end-to-end

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monitoring. These approaches aim to optimize performance across the entire edge-cloud continuum [5], [11]. For in-transit processing, new algorithms are proposed that enable processing application requests opportunistically on computing devices along the cloud continuum path. This approach has shown significant improvements in reducing network saturation compared to traditional routing strategies [12]. To optimize resource allocation, previous research has investigated formal orchestration models for in-transit processing in cloud continuum environments [13]. These models aim to optimize resource allocation in heterogeneous computing facilities, including micro data centers and intermediate computing nodes. For data-driven performance modeling, advanced techniques leveraging systems theory, optimization theory, and game theory are being applied to develop data-driven performance models for edge computing systems. These models aim to provide predictability in the context of complex edge cloud infrastructures [14]. For adaptive system design, there is a focus on developing adaptive system designs that can automate resource reservation and task allocation in large edge infrastructures [15]. These designs address challenges such as load balancing, lifecycle management, and detection and mitigation of latency/reliability anomalies while maintaining predictability for running applications.

More recently, with the advent of quantum computing, researchers have begun to explore its potential to overcome the limitations of classical algorithms in complex network environments. Authors in [16] investigated the use of quantum-inspired algorithms for network routing, showing that quantum approaches could significantly reduce computation times in specific scenarios. However, their work did not consider edge-cloud orchestration scenario and primarily focused on theoretical aspects to identify optimal pareto front rather than points when quantum search can surpass classical search in simulations. Similarly, paper in [17], a quantum computing framework for network optimization was introduced to maximize data accuracy in a real-time environment. However, due to the experimental limitations of IoT applications, the study was limited to simple topologies and did not consider multi-objective optimization in edge-cloud orchestration scenario for path optimization.

While the above studies have laid the foundation for the integration of quantum computing into network orchestration, there is still a research gap that focuses on practical, scalable solutions that meet the diverse and dynamic requirements of edge cloud environments. Our paper advances the field of network orchestration in edge cloud environments by providing a comprehensive and practical framework that directly integrates quantum computing algorithms into the orchestration of edge cloud networks.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

In edge cloud networks, service management is about selecting the most efficient paths for data transfer and resource allocation. The network can be represented as a set of interconnected nodes, where each node can be either an edge

device or a cloud server and the connections between them are communication links. Each node has specific attributes, such as available processing power, memory, storage capacity and bandwidth. Similarly, each connection between the nodes has attributes such as latency, data transmission rates, reliability and error metrics, all of which affect the overall service quality.

The goal of this problem is to find an optimal path that efficiently routes service requests while satisfying various performance constraints. A service request originates from a source node and must reach a destination node, satisfying requirements such as computational power, memory, storage, bandwidth, latency and reliability. The selected path should minimize latency, error rates and packet loss while maximizing reliability and bandwidth efficiency. At the same time, the path must ensure that none of the nodes or communication links exceed its available resource limits. To achieve this, we define a multi-objective optimization problem that balances various factors of network performance. The solution must satisfy several constraints, including resource availability at each node, bandwidth and latency requirements along the chosen path, and reliability considerations to ensure stable communication. The challenge is to find a path that meets all of these conditions while optimizing the overall efficiency of the network. Since the optimization problem can involve several competing objectives, it can be formulated as a weighted sum of different performance metrics. These include latency, error rates, bandwidth utilization and reliability, which are combined into a single function for evaluation. The complexity of the problem arises from the large number of potential paths and constraints, making it computationally difficult to solve using conventional methods. Given the nonlinear nature of the optimization function, conventional optimization techniques may be insufficient, so heuristic or quantum-based search methods are explored as possible solutions. Quantum computing can offer a potential advantage in handling large search spaces and enables faster identification of optimal paths compared to classical search algorithms. The next sections discuss the implementation of quantum search approach and its potential benefits for edge cloud orchestration.

III. DYNAMIC PROGRAMMING ALGORITHMS

DP is a basic technique for solving optimization problems by breaking them down into overlapping subproblems and solving each subproblem only once. This method is particularly effective for problems where recursive solutions have redundancy, as it efficiently stores intermediate results to avoid redundant computations. In this section, we explore two approaches to dynamic programming: the classical DP method that yields exact solutions by systematically evaluating all possible states, and a quantum-enhanced version that uses the Grover search algorithm for acceleration, inspired by the methods described in [18], which explore the combination of Grover's quantum search with partial dynamic programming to achieve quantum speedups for classical DP problems with exponential time. While the classical DP algorithm serves as

a benchmark due to its deterministic and exact nature, the Quantum DP algorithm aims to achieve quadratic speedup in the exploration of solution spaces and thus offers a promising way to tackle computationally intensive problems. These algorithms are analyzed and compared in terms of runtime and accuracy for different problem instances.

A. Classical Dynamic Programming

Algorithm 1 provides the pseudo-code for classical DP algorithm. The algorithm begins by initializing a dynamic programming table (dp) where each entry $dp[mask][u]$ represents the minimum cost to reach node u while visiting a subset of nodes represented by $mask$. All entries in the table are initialized to infinity (∞), except for the starting node s , which is initialized to 0. This ensures that the algorithm starts with a valid base case. Next, the algorithm iterates over all subsets of nodes, represented by bitmasks. Each bitmask ($mask$) encodes which nodes have been visited so far. For each subset, the algorithm evaluates every node u included in that subset. This ensures that all possible paths are considered. For each node u in the current subset, the algorithm explores its potential neighbors v . If a neighbor v has already been visited (i.e., it is part of the current bitmask $mask$) or there is no edge between u and v , the algorithm skips that neighbor. This pruning step avoids redundant computations and ensures only valid paths are evaluated.

The algorithm then updates the dynamic programming table by computing the minimum cost to reach each neighbor v from u , considering the new subset of visited nodes ($mask \mid (1 \ll v)$). This incremental approach ensures that all possible paths and their associated costs are evaluated efficiently. After processing all subsets of nodes, the algorithm retrieves the minimum cost to reach the end node e while visiting all nodes. This value is stored in $dp[(1 \ll n) - 1][e]$, where $(1 \ll n) - 1$ represents the bitmask indicating that all nodes have been visited. If the final cost remains infinity (∞), it implies that no valid path exists from s to e , and the algorithm returns -1 . Otherwise, it returns the computed minimum cost.

B. Quantum DP with Grover Search

The Quantum DP algorithm integrates Grover's search with dynamic programming to efficiently solve the optimal path problem of this paper (which is simplified as the shortest path). Algorithm 2 provides the pseudo-code for Quantum DP algorithm. A detailed breakdown of its steps are as follows:

- 1) *Initialization*: The algorithm begins by creating a dynamic programming table (dp) where each entry $dp[mask][u]$ represents the minimum cost to reach node u while visiting a subset of nodes represented by $mask$. The table is initialized to infinity (∞) for all entries, except for the starting node s , where the cost is set to 0.
- 2) *Iterating Over Subsets*: The algorithm iterates over all possible subsets of nodes, represented as bitmasks. Each bitmask ($mask$) indicates which nodes have been visited

Algorithm 1 Classical DP for Shortest Path

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1: Input: Graph  $G$  (adjacency matrix), Start Node  $s$ , End Node  $e$ 
2: Output: Minimum cost of the shortest path
3:
4:  $n \leftarrow$  Number of nodes in  $G$ 
5: Initialize  $dp[mask][u] \leftarrow \infty$  for all  $mask, u$ 
6:  $dp[1 \ll s][s] \leftarrow 0$   $\triangleright$  Cost to start node is 0
7: for each  $mask$  in  $[0, 2^n - 1]$  do  $\triangleright$  Iterate over all subsets of nodes
8:   for each node  $u$  in  $[0, n - 1]$  do
9:     if  $(mask \wedge (1 \ll u)) = 0$  then
10:      continue  $\triangleright$  Skip if  $u$  is not in the current subset
11:   end if
12:   for each node  $v$  in  $[0, n - 1]$  do
13:     if  $(mask \wedge (1 \ll v)) \neq 0$  or  $G[u][v] = 0$  then
14:      continue  $\triangleright$  Skip if  $v$  is already visited or no edge exists
15:     end if
16:      $dp[mask \vee (1 \ll v)][v] \leftarrow \min(dp[mask \vee (1 \ll v)][v], dp[mask][u] + G[u][v])$ 
17:   end for
18: end for
19: end for
20:  $result \leftarrow dp[(1 \ll n) - 1][e]$ 
21: if  $result = \infty$  then
22:   return  $-1$   $\triangleright$  No path found
23: else
24:   return  $result$ 
25: end if

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so far. For each subset, the algorithm evaluates each node u included in the subset.

- 3) *Exploring Neighbors*: For the current node u , the algorithm identifies the unvisited neighbors using an auxiliary function optimized with caching (using memoization) to improve performance by avoiding redundant computations.
- 4) *Grover's Search for Neighbors*: Once the neighbors are identified, the algorithm uses the Grover search to probabilistically find the neighbor v that minimizes the path cost of u . The number of Grover iterations is determined based on the square root of the number of neighbors and adjusted for accuracy. At each iteration, a neighbor is randomly selected and its cost is calculated. The best cost determined so far is updated if the newly calculated cost is lower.
- 5) *Updating the DP Table*: After evaluating the neighbors of u , the algorithm updates the DP table to reflect the minimum cost of reaching each neighbor v from u , taking into account the subset represented by the updated bitmask ($mask \mid (1 \ll v)$).
- 6) *Computing the Final Result*: Once all subsets of nodes

have been processed, the algorithm determines the minimum cost to reach the final node e while visiting all nodes. This value is stored in $dp[(1 \ll n) - 1][e]$, where $(1 \ll n) - 1$ represents the bitmask for all visited nodes.

- 7) *Handling Infeasible Solutions*: If the final cost is infinite (∞), this means that there is no valid path from s to e that visits all nodes. In this case, the algorithm returns -1 . Otherwise, it returns the calculated minimum cost.

This approach intelligently combines the quadratic speedup of Grover's Search for neighborhood search with the reusability of dynamic programming to balance accuracy and scalability. By using memoization and structured iteration, the algorithm reduces redundant computations and improves efficiency, especially for larger graphs.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. System Setup

The simulation system is configured with an x86_64 architecture featuring a 2.00GHz Intel Xeon CPU with 2 virtual CPUs, each supporting hyper-threading using Google Colab Pro in cloud environment. It has 12.7 GB of RAM. The GPU is a Tesla T4 with 15 GB of memory. The system is operating under a KVM-based virtualized environment, leveraging the NVIDIA-SMI driver version 535.104.05 and CUDA version 12.2. Disk usage has a total 201.2 GB. The Python environment uses Qiskit for quantum circuit simulation¹, so that the setup is optimized for both classical and quantum computational tasks. All results of the experiments were determined by averaging 100 runs.

B. Quantum DP Search Time Comparisons

The performance of Classical DP and Quantum DP with Grover's Search algorithms describe in Algorithm 1 and Algorithm 2 respectively in terms of their execution time and accuracy for graphs of different sizes for graph sizes of 4, 7, and 10 nodes are provided in Table I. In terms of execution time, classical DP shows faster and more predictable performance across all graph sizes. For example, it takes only 0.0002 s for graph size 4 and increases to 0.0561 s for graph size 10. This increase is exponential, which is to be expected due to the nature of DP algorithms that evaluate all subsets of nodes. On the other hand, Quantum DP is consistently slower. It takes 0.0020 s for a graph of size 4 and increases significantly to 0.4489 s for a graph of size 10. The additional overhead due to Grover's Search and the iterative path finding steps contribute to this slower performance. Accuracy is another distinguishing feature. Classical DP achieves 100% accuracy for all graph sizes because it is a deterministic algorithm designed to compute exact solutions. In contrast, the accuracy of Quantum DP decreases as the size of the graph increases. While it achieves an accuracy of 98% for graph size 4, it drops to 86% for size 7 and 50% for size 10. This decrease

¹Online: <https://dakk.github.io/qlasskit/>, Available: August 2024.

Algorithm 2 Quantum DP with Grover's Search

```

1: Input: Graph  $G$  (adjacency matrix), Start Node  $s$ , End Node  $e$ 
2: Output: Minimum cost of the shortest path
3:
4:  $n \leftarrow$  Number of nodes in  $G$ 
5: Initialize  $dp[mask][u] \leftarrow \infty$  for all  $mask, u$ 
6:  $dp[1 \ll s][s] \leftarrow 0$   $\triangleright$  Cost to start node is 0
7: for each  $mask$  in  $[0, 2^n - 1]$  do  $\triangleright$  Iterate over all subsets of nodes
8:   for each node  $u$  in  $[0, n - 1]$  do
9:     if  $(mask \wedge (1 \ll u)) = 0$  then
10:      continue  $\triangleright$  Skip if  $u$  is not in the current subset
11:     end if
12:      $neighbors \leftarrow$  Cached function to find unvisited neighbors of  $u$ 
13:     if  $neighbors \neq \emptyset$  then
14:        $grover\_runtime \leftarrow \lceil \sqrt{|neighbors|} \rceil + 10$ 
15:        $best\_neighbor\_cost \leftarrow \infty$ 
16:       for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $grover\_runtime$  do  $\triangleright$  Perform Grover's iterations
17:         Randomly select a neighbor  $v$  from  $neighbors$ 
18:          $cost \leftarrow dp[mask][u] + G[u][v]$ 
19:         if  $cost < best\_neighbor\_cost$  then
20:            $best\_neighbor\_cost \leftarrow cost$ 
21:         end if
22:          $dp[mask \vee (1 \ll v)][v] \leftarrow \min(dp[mask \vee (1 \ll v)][v], cost)$ 
23:       end for
24:     end if
25:   end for
26: end for
27:  $result \leftarrow dp[(1 \ll n) - 1][e]$ 
28: if  $result = \infty$  then
29:   return  $-1$   $\triangleright$  No path found
30: else
31:   return  $result$ 
32: end if

```

reflects the limitations of Grover's Search and the probabilistic nature of quantum algorithms that struggle with larger problem spaces.

To summarise, classical DP is more efficient and reliable, making it the preferred choice for small to medium sized graphs where both speed and accuracy are critical. Quantum DP, while utilising quantum resources, shows potential for smaller problems but faces scalability and accuracy challenges as the graph gets larger. For practical applications, classical DP is currently better suited, while quantum DP may require further optimization to effectively process larger and more

TABLE I: Comparison of Classical DP and Quantum DP with Grover Search Times and Accuracy.

Graph Size	Classical DP		Quantum DP	
	Time (s)	Accuracy (%)	Time (s)	Accuracy (%)
4	0.0002	100.00	0.0020	98.00
7	0.0034	100.00	0.0355	86.00
10	0.0561	100.00	0.4489	50.00

complex graphs.

V. PRACTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

It is also crucial to consider several practical aspects that may influence the real-world application of quantum orchestrators in edge-cloud continuum environments: (i) *Experimental Constraints and Quantum Hardware Limitations*: Our analysis used classical hardware, which inevitably biases the results towards classical algorithms. As quantum hardware continues to evolve and improve, we can expect a significant reduction in practical execution times for quantum algorithms such as Grover’s. At the same time, despite the promise of quantum computing for enhancing edge-cloud orchestration, the current state of quantum hardware presents several practical limitations that must be considered. Present-day quantum devices suffer from issues such as limited qubit counts, high error rates, short coherence times, and restricted connectivity between qubits, which pose challenges for implementing complex algorithms like Grover’s search in real-world scenarios. The limited number of qubits available in existing hardware significantly constrains the size of the problem that can be addressed, making it difficult to scale to large networks or handle complex parameter spaces. (ii) *Quantum Advantage for Intractable Problems*: Efficient quantum algorithms will be particularly valuable for certain problems where classical algorithms are computationally infeasible due to their complexity. In the context of managing edge cloud continuum services, this could include large-scale optimization problems, complex scheduling tasks, or security-related computations that are currently intractable using classical methods [19].

(iii) *Algorithm Efficiency Improvements*: Ongoing research in the field of quantum algorithms could lead to more efficient implementations or completely new algorithms. These advances would further increase the practical benefits of quantum approaches in service management. For example, improvements in quantum approximate optimization algorithms (QAOA) or the development of hybrid quantum-classical algorithms could offer significant speedups for certain orchestration and resource allocation tasks [20]. (iv) *Scalability Challenges*: On the way to practical implementations, it is important to consider the scalability of quantum orchestrators. Even though quantum algorithms offer theoretical advantages, translating them into scalable solutions for large edge cloud environments is a major technical challenge. Issues such as error correction, qubit connectivity and coherence times need to be addressed to realize the full potential of quantum orchestrators. (v) *Integration with Classical Systems*: In practice, quantum orchestrators will probably have to work together

with the existing classical infrastructure [21]. The development of efficient interfaces between quantum and classical components of the system as well as the development of hybrid algorithms that utilize the strengths of both paradigms will be crucial for practical use. (vi) *Energy Efficiency Considerations*: While quantum computers promise computational advantages, their energy consumption is an important factor to consider, especially in the context of edge computing where energy resources may be limited. Future research should investigate the energy efficiency of quantum orchestrators compared to their classical counterparts.

(vii) *Resilience and Fault Tolerance*: Edge cloud environments are inherently dynamic and prone to failure. Quantum orchestrators must be designed with resilience in mind, incorporating fault-tolerant quantum error correction techniques and robust algorithms that can handle hardware imperfections and environmental noise. (viii) *Cost-Benefit Analysis*: The economic viability of deploying quantum orchestrators in edge cloud continuum environments is an important consideration, especially as quantum hardware becomes more accessible [22]. To provide concrete guidance to potential adopters, we propose a structured framework for cost-benefit analysis that assesses both the direct and indirect effects of implementing quantum technologies. Key factors in this analysis include hardware costs, operational challenges and potential performance gains. The initial cost of acquiring or accessing quantum hardware is significant and includes expenses for purchasing quantum devices or subscribing to quantum cloud services, which often have usage-based pricing models. The costs of maintenance and infrastructure, such as special cooling systems, hardware reliability and staff training, must also be evaluated. These costs vary depending on whether the infrastructure is managed in-house or outsourced. Performance improvements are an important part of analysis, including reduced task execution time, improved optimization efficiency, and the ability to handle larger problem sizes. Quantifying these improvements in terms of operational savings or increased revenue is essential for assessing the economic value of quantum orchestrators. (ix) *Regulatory and Security Implications*: The use of quantum technologies in service management may have regulatory implications, especially in sectors with strict data protection requirements, such as healthcare, finance, and telecommunications [23]. Frameworks such as GDPR, HIPAA and other regional data protection laws impose strict requirements on the processing, storage and transmission of data that must be considered when deploying quantum-based orchestration frameworks. The dynamic and distributed nature of edge cloud

environments combined with the computing power of quantum technologies requires careful adherence to these regulatory frameworks to ensure compliance. For example, quantum algorithms can change the way data is processed and routed across different nodes, potentially impacting compliance with data privacy and retention policies. Consequently, a comprehensive orchestration approach must integrate robust data encryption, access control and compliance monitoring mechanisms to meet these regulatory requirements.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we present a novel approach for managing services in the edge-cloud continuum by integrating quantum computing, in particular Grover's search algorithm, into the orchestration process. Our work introduces a multi-objective optimization framework that considers critical parameters such as latency, bandwidth, reliability, and error rates and provides a comprehensive solution for balancing the requirements of modern network services for path optimization scenario. By developing and implementing a quantum orchestrator, the potential of quantum search algorithms is shown to efficiently explore the vast parameter space of complex network environments. Our scalability analysis shows that comparisons of two approaches to DP, namely the classical DP method and a quantum-enhanced version that uses the Grover search algorithm for acceleration, are compared in terms of accuracy and execution times. However, we also acknowledge the challenges associated with the integration of quantum computing, such as hardware limitations and the complexity of implementing quantum algorithms. Implementing quantum search in edge cloud environments, while challenging, holds promise for future advances as quantum computing technologies continue to evolve.

In future work, to address the limitations of our current approach, we will focus on implementing the proposed quantum orchestration framework on actual quantum hardware, such as IBM Quantum [24] or Google's quantum platform to validate the theoretical models and simulation results presented in this paper. This will enable us to evaluate the performance of quantum algorithms in a more practical context and different network scenarios, considering real-world hardware limitations like qubit availability, decoherence and limited, noise levels, gate errors, and coherence times.

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